

COVID-19, E-GOVERNMENT AND THE FUTURE OF REMOTE WORKING IN GHANA

Akpeko Agbevade

Department of Political Science, School of Social Sciences,
College of Humanities, University of Ghana, Legon, Ghana

Email: aagbevade@ug.edu.gh, aagbevade@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6580-5393>

Article Info

Received on: 11 Jan 2023

Accepted on: 12 Apr 2023

Available online: 10-Jun-2023

Cite This Article As

Agbevade A (2023), "Covid-19, E-Government and the Future of Remote Working in Ghana", International Journal of E-Government & E-Business Research, Volume 8, Issue 1, 2023, pp 01-19. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8012288>

©2023 By the Author. Published By ARSEAM Foundation. This article is an open access article published & distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) license. The full terms of this license may be seen at : <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>

The Journal follows the Best Practice guidelines and this statement is based on the guidelines and standards developed by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE): <https://publicationethics.org/>

ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: The primary objective of the study was to interrogate the nexus between COVID-19, e-government and the future of remote working in Ghana. In short, the paper examined how e-government was deployed to ensure the continuity of work in Ghana at the height of the COVID-19 pandemic and discussed the future of remote working in the context of the e-government apparatus.

Design/Methodology: The study was purely qualitative. Data triangulation approach was used as data were sourced from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data was obtained through interviews with both employers and employees as well as clients. Secondary data were collected from book chapters, journal articles and official publications and documents of entities. Data analysis was done using content analysis based on which themes were extracted.

Findings: The findings of the study revealed that Ghana started implementing e-government strategies prior to the COVID-19, specifically from 2017 which included; digital national identification system, Ghana Post GPS digital addressing system etc. However, it witnessed massive boost during the pandemic. Government-to-government, government-to-citizen and government-to-employee were the main models of e-government implemented. Specific e-government apparatus implemented were e-justice system, Ghana Learning TV and Radio, iCampus, iBoxes, Learning Management Systems like SAKAI, Paperless Port System, Integrated Customs Management System. These strategies were further supported by the rolling out of virtual public offices It allowed workers to connect and coordinate from afar. Over 300 different agencies have had non-departmental tasks, like payroll, digitised thanks to the rollout of smart workplace technologies. Socio-cultural and the communal system in Ghana, low level of ICT infrastructure, and capacity, unethical work values, and high cost of data among others were found to be key dynamics to undermine the future of remote working in Ghana.

Practical implications: *The study showed that the traditional system of work (employees working from a fixed physical location) is threatened in times of emergencies, pandemics and disasters hence the need for alternative(s) which is the use of digital technology. However, the alternative is not the total panacea because of the identified Achilles' heel above. The paper therefore recommends a hybrid approach where the physical and the remote systems of work exist in tandem while addressing the weaknesses of e-government.*

Originality and value: *This paper contributes to the embryonic literature on COVID-19, e-government and remote working as it does not only discuss the three variables in isolation but the linkage. It also interrogates the measures that institutions adopted to remain in operation at the height of the pandemic and examined whether the strategies are enduring. The conclusion drawn and recommendations showed that e-government is a good strategy for service delivery worth pursuing but full benefits can only be realized when the underlying challenges are addressed by initially having champions of change to canvas for the "virtual state".*

Keywords: COVID-19, remote working, e-government, Ghana

Paper type: Review paper

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19, which is considered an amorphous and wicked problem (Ayee 2022; Agbevade 2022), struck the entire world in the latter part of 2019. Historically, the COVID-19 caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS-CoV-2) was first detected in Wuhan, China on December 19, 2019. The World Health Organisation (WHO) declared it on March 11, 2020 as a global pandemic (World Health Organisation 2020b; Azizi et al. 2021). Some scholars referred to it as human and health crises (Collings et al. 2021). A joint statement by The WHO and the International Chamber of Commerce intimated that, the pandemic must be attended to head-on by state authorities to avert its spread due to its consequences on the health and economic sectors of nation-states (Azizi et al. 2021). Organisations across all sectors (public and private) were not exempted from its devastating effect. In response, organisations formulated and implemented strategies to keep them in operation for the purposes of attaining organizational bottom lines (profit). For instance, Collings et al. (2021) intimated that the COVID-19 has changed the experience of work for most employees due to organisational policy interventions.

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic did not spare Ghanaian organisations. In fact, the impact was severe since that was the first pandemic experienced coupled with the absence of policy measures to contain it. As such, knee-jerk strategies were adopted. Prevalent among the strategies was remote working. This paper discusses the e-government strategies implemented to ensure organisational operations through remote working as well as examining the future of remote working in Ghana's working space. Specifically, the paper seeks to address two key objectives. These are to discuss the e-government strategies deployed in Ghana in the midst of the COVID-19 and examine the future of remote working in the context of the e-government apparatus.

The argument of the paper is that the wake of the COVID-19 came with remote working driven by e-government interventions. However, the future of remote working in Ghana is bleak and pessimistic due to multiplicity of factors including the socio-cultural and communal nature of the Ghanaian society, low level of ICT infrastructure, high ICT illiteracy rate, poor work ethics and parochial employee interests among others. As a prognosis, the study opines that at best, organisations in Ghana can practice a hybrid system of work where the physical system exists alongside the remote working system with the former having a higher proportion.

Methodologically, the study employed data triangulation approach where qualitative interviews were conducted among workers and employers. Secondary data was sourced from journal articles as well as official publications of the Government of Ghana on the subject matter. Content analysis was used to analyze the collected data. Data collection was done between October, 2022 and January, 2023.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: section two reviews literature on remote working, section three deals with Ghana's response to the COVID-19, section four discusses COVID-19 and remote working nexus, section five addresses the e-government apparatus in Ghana, section six focuses on the future of remote working in Ghana. Section seven concentrates on the conclusion and recommendations.

2. SCHOLARSHIP ON REMOTE WORKING: A REVIEW OF THE EXTANT LITERATURE

The literature on remote working is fragmented as researchers have interrogated the terminology from diverse perspectives. Workers are increasingly able to contact with their company and participate in more flexible working practises through the use of remote working, which is defined as working from home or another location outside of an office at any time (Grant et al. 2013; Wang et al. 2021). Thus with remote working, the employee works outside the prescribed physical work environment. It is driven by the use of digital technologies such as the internet, computers among others. The success of remote working heavily hinges on a robust information communication technology (ICT) (Ko et al. 2021; O'Farrell and Montagnier 2020). Remote working has gained currency in modern times because of advances in technology and the yearning of employees to work remotely (Gifford 2022) coupled with the outbreak of the coronavirus.

Studies on the subject matter of remote working have centered on the advantages and disadvantages with emphasis on the economic-financial benefits. Allen et al. (2015) for instance examined the merits of remote working from the productivity perspectives. Mas and Pallais (2017) interrogated the concept from the angle of salary status while Moen et al. (2011) argued on how remote working influences employee retention. In addition, lower travel, clothing, and out-of-pocket costs were identified as some specific economic-financial benefits of remote

working inuring to the employee. Other scholars also enumerated factors such as Positive consequences of remote work include increased job satisfaction, productivity, independence, work-life balance, and reduced work-family conflict (Allen et al. 2015; Gajendran and Harrison 2007). On the negatives, social isolation, dissatisfaction, work life imbalance, gender inequality and technostress have been identified (Biron et al. 2021; Ruiller et al. 2019; Ingusci et al. 2021). Researchers have dichotomous views on the relationship between remote working and work life balance. Whereas Irawanto et al. (2021) postulates that it helps improve work life balance, Como et al. (2021); Fuller and Hirsh (2019); Golden and Wiens-Tuers (2006) hold contrary views. Contributing to the merits and demerits of remote working, Battisti et al. (2022) opined that not all the gains and setbacks could be monetized. They instead adduced to the fact that some of these have relational and psychological impacts on employees.

On gender and remote working, scholars are unanimous that the latter helps to bridge gender gaps in the labour market (Arntz et al. 2019; Bloom et al. 2015; Golden et al. 2014). In the words of Angelici and Profeta (2020), the flexibility associated with remote working (flexible location, time etc) makes it very attractive for both sexes. They further asserted that remote working narrows the gender gaps because it improves women's work-life balance and invites men to participate more in housework and care activities (2020). This position is echoed by Del Boca et al. (2021) who found that Gender inequality was reduced as males took on more responsibilities at home and in the care of their children as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic.

Studies also examined the nexus between age group and remote working. Gallacher and Hossain (2020) in their study found that older workers were disadvantaged when remote working was deployed because the strategy denied them of interaction with their colleagues, difficulty in WLB, and low level of technological capacity whiles relatively younger employees benefited from the strategy because they were ICT savvy.

On the relationship between employment status and remote working, scholars found that workers who work independently like managers and self-employed preferred remote working since they can save commuting time and costs (Edmans 2011). In a related manner, Barrero et al. (2021) and Bonacini et al. (2021) also espoused that workers with higher remunerations derived greater satisfaction from remote working.

Additional charges for digital technology and platforms were found to have a negative and significant economic-financial impact in a study by Battisti et al. (2022) on remote work and digital technology. Personal computer, internet connection, licenses for instant communication platforms, and cloud sharing space were spotted as some costs employees incurred working remote. In addition, employees forfeited benefits such as non-payment of overtime and meal vouchers. According to Battisti et al. (2022) the forfeited benefits far outweighed the costs they would have incurred in going to work.

Gifford (2022) took the notch higher by examining the impact of digital and remote working on workload and intensity and found a mixed relationship. Regular ICT connection

negates the work-life boundaries by enhancing ‘always on’ work climates (Schlachter et al. 2018). Though this increases employee availability, it significantly contributes to techno stress and pressure on employees’ time for work. On the contrary, there are benefits from remote working as it results in reduced commuting times. For example, According to a CIPD poll, the average UK worker spends about four hours commuting each week, with that number increasing to 6.5 hours for Londoners (Wheatley and Gifford, 2019). Gifford (2022) found that, after weighing the pros and cons, it's important to keep an eye on how much time people spend working from home.

Working remotely hinders efficient interaction. This is because electronic forms of communication diminish the usage of social cues that contribute to the development of interpersonal bonds (Lin et al., 2008). Working from home has an effect on the social climate and workplace connections. Several factors have been identified as predictors of mental discomfort (Barends et al. 2021; Finne, et al. 2016), including the presence or absence of an encouraging and supportive, calm, or distrustful work environment. A 2020 survey found that half of UK home workers felt their work relationships had suffered as a result, and 56% of those with existing mental health issues felt deteriorated, lending credence to the idea that many workers are missing social contact after two years of dominance by the pandemic lockdown.

Remote working also places demands on the capacity of human resource managers. Evidence exists that organizations that implemented remote working well during the pandemic had managers who concentrated on macro issues such as corporate objectives instead of micro-managing inputs (Felstead 2022). Human resources professionals and business leaders had a view that "people managers play a critical role in supporting effective remote working," underscoring the need to hone this skill (Delany 2021). Agbevade (2022) echoed same position that due to limited monitoring capacity and measures, remote working in Ghana at the height of the pandemic failed to yield the expected performance from employees. It is therefore imperative that HR managers must equally acquire the requisite skills needed to march the demands of remote working.

The impact of remote work on productivity has been found to be inconsistent (Gifford 2022). Researchers Ortiz de Guinea et al. (2012) found that working remotely can pose challenges compared to in-person collaboration.

Chen (2021) identified four major challenges to remote working. These are; the requirement for employees to acquire new knowledge, skills and abilities (KSAs) in online learning as well as virtual skills communication, the absence of face-to-face touch to communication in solving workplace related problems and its associated hindrances like psychological stress and anxiety. Others include sacrificing of family time for work issues leading to family-work conflict with the resultant impact on productivity and the tendency for employees to ignore organisational culture.

3. GHANA’S RESPONSE TO THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

On March 12, 2020, Ghana recorded its first two cases of the corona virus (Ghana Health Service 2020). As a step in addressing the outbreak, the Government of Ghana observed the spread for couple of weeks across the globe and the strategies implemented by nation states in de-escalating the spread. Following the outcome of the observations, the authorities in Ghana did not adopt the prescriptions of the WHO hook, line and sinker but varied it to satisfy the specific environmental needs of the State because there is no one-fit-for-all approach in dealing with this wicked problem. Suspending public gatherings, disinfecting market facilities, enforcing social distance and good personal hygiene, closing all land, sea, and air borders to human traffic, and locking down disease hotspots were the primary general strategies used to contain the spread of the virus (Asante and Mills, 2020). Following these broad restrictions, on March 15, 2020, the Head of State gave a countrywide address and declared a four-week ban on all public meetings. To back up the government's pledge to combat the epidemic, parliament passed the Imposition of Restrictions Act 2020 (Act 1012). Executive Instrument 64: Imposition of Restrictions (Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic) Instrument, 2020 (Republic of Ghana, 2020c) implements the Act. The Act suspended or restricted the following rights enjoyed by Ghanaians and residents of Ghana:

- (i) the right to education (closure of schools)
- (ii) freedom of religion (suspension of services in churches and mosques)
- (iii) cultural rights (funeral and private burials limited to 25 persons in attendance)
- (iv) freedom of association (suspension of conferences, workshops)
- (v) political rights and freedom of expression (suspension of political rallies)
- (vi) leisure (sporting events) and
- (vii) movement (travel advisory, lockdown, closure of the country's borders) (Appiagyei-Atua 2020).

In exercising the powers granted him under the Act and the E.I., the President on March 27, 2020 announced a partial lockdown to take effect from March 30, 2020 in areas considered epicenters of the pandemic (President of Ghana March 27, 2020). The specific areas were the Greater Accra and Greater Kumasi. The announcement of the partial lockdown had implications for how and where organisations and their employees operated. Ghana like other countries across the globe embraced remote working also known as working from home (WFH) and teleworking as a mechanism for reducing human contacts aimed at reducing the spread of the virus. The remote working cut across all sectors (public and private) of the economy (education, commerce, manufacturing etc). Employees in organisation's that provides essential services were allowed to go to work under strict conditions. The implementation of the remote working strategy hinged on the use of e-government apparatus which is discussed in the paper.

4. DISCOURSE ON COVID-19 AND REMOTE WORKING

The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has witnessed scholars researching into the relationship between the pandemic and remote working. Attesting to this is Felstead's (2022) calculation that in UK, newspaper articles on WFH rose from about 150 a month before the pandemic to nearly 6,000 a month in March 2020. Some of these studies are reviewed below.

In order to create national policies for effective human resource management, Davidescu et al. (2020) studied how different forms of remote work, including fully remote work, partially remote work, flex offices, and coworking, affected job satisfaction and productivity among Romanian workers. Based on their findings, it appears that the primary types of workplace flexibility, such as working from home and high employee turnover, have been implemented in the Romanian labour market. Romanian workers felt that the approach was adopted, but that shift work, flexible scheduling, and overtime were not adequately addressed. Although employees expressed strong interest in and support for a work-from-home policy, it was only partially implemented.

The spread of the COVID-19 and associated losses could be mitigated, according to Zou et al. (2020b), because many businesses opted for flexible work practises including working from home. Most individuals were already using WFH, digital enterprises, and online shopping when the COVID-19 pandemic hit. Work habits shifted, and the WFH model gained popularity, as a direct result of the crisis's onset.

Using a gender lens, we analysed the possible links between remote employment and COVID-19. During the COVID-19 epidemic, fathers became more involved in their children's lives, helping to even the gender playing field (Del Boca et al., 2021).

Researchers also looked at HR managers' responsibilities in the context of telecommuting during the COVID-19 pandemic. During COVID-19, the HR manager must serve as a leader for the organisation and its staff. Human resource managers may find more success with a crisis-driven approach to HR. According to them, managing people is considerably simpler than managing other resources in a crisis. High-level strategic integration between job skills, stress alleviation, work-family balance, and corporate culture is necessary for designing crisis management systems (Wang et al., 2021). Human resources should take a different tack in times of crises than other departments. Human resource managers counter organisational crises by practising crisis management readiness (Lockwood, 2005), which entails bolstering the morale of employees and reducing stress levels. The crisis management awareness of HR practitioners can mitigate the effects of COVID-19 on four fronts—work skill development, psychological stress reduction, work-life balance, and cultural role—which are all crucial to the company's existence (Chen 2021).

Additional polls strengthened the correlation between the two factors. In July 2020, for example, studies confirmed that the lockdown had a more positive than negative effect on attitudes towards remote work: 6 in 10 UK remote workers said they were more likely to request WFH in the future, while only 5% said they were less likely to do so (Gifford and Green, 2020).

An employee study in the United States indicated that workers valued WFH at 7% to 8% of compensation on average (Barrero et al., 2021). The longer-term trend anticipated was that, having examined alternatives, employees would expect to exert pressure on employers to cater more for WFH. Some businesses considered whether they could force employees scared of COVID-19 to return to the office (Hoeritzauer 2022).

It has been projected that WFH is not a practical alternative for many workers and may not be a preference for others due to the challenges involved with it, despite the fact that remote working greatly assisted work to proceed largely while the epidemic was at its peak. In fact, the epidemic may have shown that some jobs aren't suited to being performed from afar. Those who did not request flexible scheduling in the summer of 2020 were even less likely to do so in the future, according to a survey conducted in the United Kingdom (Gifford and Green, 2020). Conflicts between employees and their superiors are to be expected in some workplaces. As more workers demand the flexibility to work from home, businesses have been eager to get their workers back in the office, where they can benefit from in-person communication and build stronger working connections.

From the above reviews, studies exist on remote working and COVID-19 predominantly in the developed world but most were general with no explicit focus on a specific entity. In Ghana, the studies were general. Explicit empirical studies was by Agbevade (2022) which discussed the HRM responses to the COVID-19, impact on WLB and productivity. The current paper does not only extend the burgeoning literature on COVID-19, but also connects it to e-government mechanisms implemented and the future of remote working in Ghana.

5. E-GOVERNMENT APPARATUS IN GHANA

E-government is the practise of government entities using information and communication technologies to better serve the public. It includes the use of "database, networking, discussion support, multimedia, automation, tracking and tracing, and personal identification technologies" (Jaeger and Thompson, 2003) accessible via the internet and the world wide web. E-government has been called "digital government" and "virtual state" by its detractors (Fountain, 2001).

It's fascinating to know that e-government in Ghana was already in place before the COVID-19 appeared. Ghana launched its first e-government projects in 2005. The GGEA subsequently pushed for the adoption of the e-Government Interoperability Framework (e-GIF) by the Ghanaian government. Interoperability among government agencies' data and information resources, ICT, and electronic business processes is the goal of the e-GIF's policies, technical standards, and guidelines. Using a standard set forth by open (i.e., non-proprietary) international standards, it enables any Ministry, Department, or Agency (MDA) to integrate its data, IT, and processes with those of any other MDA. The e-GIF's primary goal is to improve government service delivery to citizens and businesses by connecting the various branches of government. The goal of the framework is to facilitate communication across different levels of government, including interactions with citizens and communities, employees, businesses, and other governments (National Information Technology Agency, 2014).

In 2017, the government's vision of digitization breathed new life into e-government as part of an initiative to make Ghana a leading digital ecosystem in Africa. As a result, several different online government projects were developed and launched. The launch of the Ghana Post GPS digital address system and the distribution of digital national identification cards (Ghana Cards) were two of the most prominent examples. The Paperless Port System (PPS), the Electronic Immigration System (EIS), the Electronic Cabinet (e-Cabinet), the Electronic Parliament, and the Electronic Procurement Portal have all been adopted by the government.

The penchant for e-government was accelerated at the height of the pandemic when a lockdown was announced in March, 2020. To facilitate distant work and teamwork, the government has implemented virtual public offices. Over 300 different agencies have had non-department-specific tasks, such as payroll, digitised thanks to the rollout of smart workplace technologies.

Various facets of the state implemented e-government strategies to ensure continuity of work at the behest of the COVID-19. The Judiciary for instance implemented an e-justice system. The e-Justice Project was launched by the Ministry of Communication and Digitalization (the hub of Ghana's e-government) and the Judicial Services of Ghana as part of the broader e-Transform Ghana Initiative. Before the lockdowns, the project's goal was to use digital tools to enhance Accra's high courts' case management as well as their administrative and financial procedures. Electronic case filing and a central, searchable e-Docket for all submitted court processes were among the characteristics of the e-Justice platform. Judges and their clerks benefited from the new digital and paperless environment by having easier access to case schedules, and lawyers and clerks were able to examine those schedules.

At the education front, e-government measures such as Ghana Learning TV and radio were implemented. This allowed lessons to be delivered to basic school pupils. At the secondary school level, iCampus was employed. As a result, students in schools supported by the World Bank's Secondary Education Improvement Project had offline access to video classes, syllabi, and virtual laboratories on iBoxes. Tertiary institutions also deployed Learning Management Systems such as Sakai to make it possible for lecturers and students to have lectures and other academic activities online.

At the ports of Ghana, the Paperless Port System (PPS) e-government was enhanced during the pandemic. From the submission of paperwork until the shipment of cleared products, the technology automated every step of the procedure. The result was a reduction in clearance times from three days to 24 hours and a consolidation of thirteen regulatory bodies down to three. The PPS aided clearing of goods during the lockdown period because clearance was done without the physical presence of agents. This reduced human contacts thereby deepening social distancing. The Integrated Customs Management System (ICUMS), or UNIPASS, was introduced by the Ghana Revenue Authority as improvement of the PPS in April, 2020. One major characteristic of the ICUMS was the further removal of human interaction and red tape,

which are considered the Achilles' heel of Ghana's public sector. In addition, In order to expedite customs clearance, the system enabled clearing agents to prepay duties prior to the shipment's arrival. With the advent of e-payments, fees may be paid through card or mobile money, allowing goods forwarders and importers to process payments remotely. Although there were a few teething problems upon implementation, the ICUMS allowed Takoradi Port to keep running even when under lockdown.

Three main models of digital government were deployed in Ghana's public sector at the pick of the pandemic. These were Government to Government (G2G), Government to Citizen (G2C) and Government to Employee (G2E). Government to Government refers to the interaction between government institutions. This is evidenced in the study by the GRA coming up with the PPS and ICUMS to be implemented by the Ghana Ports and Harbours Authority. The G2C model permits government institutions and officials to use state institution's websites, emails to inform citizens (clients) of government operations and allows clients to transact businesses with the state institutions online thereby reducing physical human interactions and enforcing social distancing the buzzword at the time. For instance, Agbevade (2022) revealed that through the application of e-government apparatus at the Driver and Vehicle Licensing Authority (DVLA), clients (customers) were provided services in application for license, renewal of roadworthy certificates, and vehicle registration among others. With e-government, the employees periodically updated clients on the state of their requests to reduce congestion and make room for social distancing at the various stations of the DVLA. The updates were done through emails, telephone calls and text messages. Furthermore, the use of e-government during the pandemic has been found to be worthy. Public perception of the virtual state recorded some positive outcomes. From June to December 2020, we polled 1964 residents of Ghana and found that the vast majority saw digital governance projects as a way to decrease corruption, increase productivity, and encourage greater citizen e-participation in government. Sixty-eight percent of people who used a digital government service said it was helpful, saves time, and is simple to use. The G2E made room for state institutions to interact with its employees on human resource management related issues such as employee leave, pay slip and reporting mechanisms which allowed for performance management and tracking of employee activities.

6. THE FUTURE OF REMOTE WORKING IN GHANA

The emergence of the coronavirus has underscored the importance of remote working strategies. In response, the government through the Ministry of Communication and Digitalization proactively formulated and executed the G2G, G2E and G2C models of e-government for continuity of work and productivity. These strategies greatly contributed to free flow of work to a large extent because of the remote working inherent in them. However, these strategies cannot allow for remote working in perpetuity in Ghana's working landscape. Significant reasons accounts for this position thereby making the future of remote working in Ghana very bleak and pessimistic. The factors are:

First, the socio-cultural and communal nature of the Ghanaian society. The Ghanaian

society is traditionally characterized by togetherness and communalism instead of individualism. As such, people including workers often yearn to be in the company of their work colleagues to work. On the other hand, remote working especially at the time of the COVID-19 lockdown discouraged this togetherness and rather encouraged social distancing. This did not auger well for most workers. For instance a respondent averred ***“I cannot continue with this thing called WFH, I missed my mates at work during the three weeks of partial lockdown and when we resumed and were running shift, I hardly met my office mates”***. With this mentality of workers, most of them (workers) were eager to resume face-to-face work so they can interact and relate with their colleagues.

Second, underdeveloped ICT infrastructure. Though efforts have been made to upgrade the IT infrastructure of the country over the years, however, more needs to be done if remote working is to be the new game in town. In Ghana, there is poor internet connectivity which is the driver of remote working. The IT capacity of most institutions is weak thereby making their systems very slow and causing unnecessary internet traffic and jams when the service users get onto the platforms of the service providers. The worst of all is the erratic supply of electricity. As succinctly put by a respondent ***“you get online to transact business and the system takes forever to upload and download”***. Another respondent also indicated ***“Sometimes you are on the service providers platform and the message you receive is this site is not available, with this I have no option than to go to the premises of the organisation for my service”***. A public sector employee stated ***“this remote working is good but it cannot be sustained because our system is not strong enough. Sending a common email with attachment is problematic; you end up spending the entire time just to do something simple. It is frustrating and stressful***. From these, it can be inferred that the low level of IT infrastructure does not affect just the employees’ ability to WFH but also the clients’ (customers) ability to access services. In addition, the long period of waiting by employees to perform their roles results in technostress. Technostress in this context means the use of technology becoming a stressor for employees. The stressor here is the quantum of time spent in getting a simple job down due to system incapacity.

The third factor making the future of remote working in Ghana non-assuring is the low level of digitalization literacy and capacity of the labour force. In the words of Ayee (2008), in the African public sector, ICT fail or underperform more often than they succeed, because ‘saints’ (progressive government staff) are few; ‘wizards’ (technical assistance staff) are inappropriate and ‘demons’ (corrupt apathetic officials) are many. With these technological deficits, most employees cannot use the ICT infrastructure independently not to talk of working with it remotely. It is interesting to note that some employees who refer to themselves as ‘born before computers’ (BBC) in Ghana prefer to still do things manually instead of using the computer. With this mindset, remote working cannot fully survive in Ghana’s working space. Related to this is the limited ICT capacity of citizens (clients). The ICT literacy rate in Ghana is very low hence; most clients also prefer physical human interaction when seeking services thereby undermining remote working. A household survey on ICT in Ghana revealed that 47.9%

and 46.1% of Ghanaians owned basic phones and smart phones respectively while a paltry 12.8% possessed feature phones. Also, 55.9% of people aged 5 and up have their own Subscriber Identification Module (SIM) cards, according to the findings. A total of 7.9% of people aged 5 and up own a computer; of those, 5.1% own laptops, 1.2% own desktops, and 1.6% own tablets. This means that 84.2% of the population does not have access to a personal computer of any kind. According to the survey's findings, 56.6% of internet users are aged five and up, while 39.7% of the general population has some understanding of what the internet is. The poll also found that among Ghana's internet users aged five and up, 73.8% regularly engage in internet-based telephone communication. Additionally, it was found that 40.8% of Ghanaians aged 5 and up have used mobile money at least once. As of March 2020 (National Communications Authority and Ghana Statistical Service, March 2020), 16.8% of homes had access to the internet.

Fourthly, the nature of most services provided in Ghana's public sector requires physical human interaction even though some commence their processes digitally. For example, Ghana has a biometric passport system that requires citizens to apply for passport online, however, along the line, clients are given appointment dates to report at the Passport Office for their bi-data and other information to be taken. Similarly, with DVLA, customers are allowed by means of e-government apparatus to transact businesses such as vehicle registration online but must physically send the vehicle to the Authority's office for inspection, same as acquiring and renewing driver's license and roadworthy certificate. Same applies to other regulatory agencies like the Ghana Standards Authority, Food and Drugs Authority etc.

The fifth reason for the pessimistic future of remote working in Ghana is low ethical values and parochialism of employees. Ethics refers to an individual's ability to behave as expected by an organisation or society irrespective of one's personal interest or condition (Buabeng, 2020). At the heart of ethics are professionalism and conscience. When the behaviour of employees is guided by professionalism and conscience, their actions will be ethical *ceteris paribus* and the reverse is true. However, in the Ghanaian context, most employees are unethical and the few who decide to be ethical are considered odd and ostracized. This undermines remote working because when employees act unethical in remote working aided by IT infrastructure, the consequences are grave and dire. Typical example is the exposé at the Ghana Education Service' (GES) Computerized School Placement System where officials collected money from citizens to change the schools for them. Employees act unethically for reasons such as poor conditions of service hence they engage in rent seeking and other corrupt activities to make ends meet. It could be recalled that in the recent past, the labour front of Ghana was characterized with labour agitations and industrial strikes in demand for better conditions of service.

The sixth factor is resistance to change. Remote working is a novelty in the work lexicon of Ghana. As such, employees would oppose it. In fact, the opposition to it is also borne from the benefits that employees derive from their physical presence and interactions. Some of the benefits include tips and facilitation gifts from clients and extortion. It could be recalled that in

December 2022, some officials of the DVLA were reported through undercover investigative journalism extorting money from prospective clients in need of drivers' license. With these benefits and acts, workers as rational beings will oppose any policy decision to make remote working a norm in Ghana.

Other factors likely to undermine remote working in Ghana are the high cost of data, concentration of ICT in the major towns and cities to the neglect of the countryside, work-family conflict culminating in work life balance challenges, absence of effective supervision and monitoring mechanisms when remote working.

7. CONCLUSION

The paper discussed the nexus between COVID-19, e-government and the future of remote working in Ghana. The paper found that the emergence of the pandemic and the subsequent lockdown announced by the President made organisations to have no other option to ensure productivity but to remote work. The major tool deployed in the remote working was the e-government apparatus with G2G, G2E and G2C models featuring prominently across the public sector. Various sectors of the state thus the judicial, education, ports etc employed various forms of e-government strategies to survive and thrive. It is also striking to note that the Government was proactive in the adoption of these e-government apparatus as the process of e-government was reignited in 2017. It also came to light that the future of remote working in Ghana is not bright but gloomy and pessimistic because of the stuck socio-cultural and communal nature of Ghanaian societies, low level of ICT infrastructure, unethical values, resistance to change, limited technological knowledge and technostress among others.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above, the paper recommends that for remote working to be internalized in the Ghanaian working space;

1. There must be champions or change agents of remote working who should spearhead the agenda. These change agents should work on the psyche of both employers and employees to appreciate the importance and the benefits of remote working. They should also ensure that the right infrastructure are in place for successful e-government policy leading to effective remote working.
2. A robust ICT infrastructure should be developed across the country. The ICT infrastructure should reduce the tendency of human influence and should be user friendly.
3. Intentional capacity building strategies should be embarked upon to develop the knowledge, skills and abilities (KSAs) of employees and clients. This can be done by stepping up ICT literacy programmes from the basic level of education.
4. The cost of data should be minimized so organisations, employees and citizens can afford to buy for purposes of remote working and other online transactions.

Though the paper strongly argued that the future of remote working in Ghana is not promising, nevertheless, improvement can be made if policy makers take the above recommendations seriously. If done, at best, a hybrid system of working where remote working will exist alongside the physical system with the latter dominating in the Ghanaian working landscape.

9. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The study was restricted to COVID-19, e-government and remote working in Ghana's public sector. In addition, qualitative method was used. It is recommended that future studies expand to look at e-governance across both the public and private sectors to assess the future of working from home in general. In addition, further research on the subject matter could consider the use of the mixed method with expanded sample size.

Acknowledgements: I appreciate the benevolence of respondents in volunteering information and authors whose research works have been referenced.

Source of funding: There was no funding for this study.

Conflict of interest: There is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Agbevade, A. (2022). "Human Resource Management Response to the Covid-19 Pandemic in Ghana's Public Sector: The Experience of the Driver and Vehicle Licensing Authority (DVLA)", *International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research*, 9(2), 2022, 1-19, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3407944>.
- Allen, T. D., T.D. Golden, and K.M. Shockley (2015). How effective is telecommuting? Assessing the status of our scientific findings, *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 16(2), 40–68. DOI:[10.1177/1529100615593273](https://doi.org/10.1177/1529100615593273)
- Angelici, M., and P. Profeta (2020). Smart working: work flexibility without constraints. CESifo Working Paper No. 8165, Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3556304>, Accessed on January 25, 2023.
- Arntz, M., B.Y. Sarra, and F. Berlingieri (2019). Working from home: Heterogeneous effects on hours worked and wages. ZEW-Centre for European Economic Research Discussion Paper, (19-015). DOI:[10.2139/ssrn.3383408](https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3383408)
- Appiagyei-Attua, K. (2020). Emergency without a State of Emergency: Effects of Imposition of Restrictions Act, 2020 on rights of Ghanaians. Retrieved from www.myjoyonline.com, Accessed on January 31, 2023.

- Asante, L.A., and R.O. Mills (2020). “Exploring the Socioeconomic impact of COVID-19 Pandemic in Marketplaces in Urban Ghana”, *Africa Spectrum*, 55(2), 170–181. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002039720943612>
- Ayee, J.R.A. (2008). *Reforming the African Public Sector: Retrospect and Prospects*, Dakar: Council for the Development of Social Science Research in Africa. Retrieved from <https://publication.codesria.org/index.php/pub/catalog/book/149>
- Ayee, J.R.A. (2022). Reflections on Ghana’s public policy space and wicked problems today; *GIMPA Quarterly*, 2(5), 10-51.
- Azizi, M.R., R. Atlasi, A. Ziapour, J. Abbas, and R. Naemi (2021). Innovative human resource management strategies during the COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic narrative review approach, *Heliyon*, (7). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07233>
- Barrero, J. M., N. Bloom, and S.J. Davis (2021). Why working from home will stick (No. w28731), National Bureau of Economic Research. DOI 10.3386/w28731
- Battisti, E., S. Alfiero, and E. Leonidou (2022). “Remote working and digital transformation during the COVID-19 pandemic: Economic–financial impacts and psychological drivers for employees”, *Journal of Business Research*, 150, 38-50. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.06.010>
- Barends, E., E. Wietrak, I. Cioca, and D.M. Rousseau (2021). “Mental Wellbeing and Digital Work: An Evidence Review.” *Scientific Summary* Retrieved from <https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/culture/wellbeing/evidence-mental-wellbeing>.
- Barrero, J. M., N. Bloom, and S. J. Davis (2021). “Why Working from Home Will Stick.” National Bureau of Economic Research Working Paper Series, Issue. <http://www.nber.org/papers/w28731> Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3741644
- Biron, M., H. De Cieri, I. Fulmer, C.H.V. Lin, W. Mayrhofer, and M. Nyfoudi (2021). Structuring for innovative responses to human resource challenges: A skunk works approach. *Human Resource Management Review*, 31(2). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2020.100768>
- Bloom, N., J. Liang, J. Roberts, and Z.J. Ying (2015). Does working from home work? Evidence from a Chinese experiment, *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 130(1), 165–218. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26372598>
- Bonacini, L., G. Gallo, and F. Patriarca (2021). “Identifying policy challenges of COVID-19 in hardly reliable data and judging the success of lockdown measures”, *Journal of Population Economics*, 34(1), 275–301. DOI: [10.1007/s00148-020-00799-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00148-020-00799-x)
- Buabeng, T. (2020). *Fundamentals of public administration and management*. Tema: Digibooks

- Chen, Z. (2021). "Influence of Working from home during the COVID-19 Crisis and HR Practitioner Response", *Front. Psychol.* 12:710517. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.710517
- CIPD, (2020) 3 September. "Impact of COVID-19 on Working Lives." Retrieved from CIPD. <https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/work/trends/goodwork/covid-impact>, Accessed on January 29, 2023.
- Collings, D.G. J. McMackin, J. Anthony, A.J. Nyberg, and P.M. Wright (2021). *Journal of Management Studies* 58(5), 1378-1382. doi: [10.1111/joms.12695](https://doi.org/10.1111/joms.12695)
- Como, R., L. Hambley, and J. Domene (2021). "An exploration of work-life wellness and remote work during and beyond COVID-19", *Canadian Journal of Career Development*, 20(1), 46–56. Retrieved from <https://cjcd-rcdc.ceric.ca/index.php/cjcd/article/view/92>
- Davidescu, A.A., S.A. Apostu, A. Paul, and I. Casuneanu (2020). "Work flexibility, job satisfaction and job performance among Romanian employees-Implications for sustainable human resource management", *Sustainability*, 12(15). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12156086>
- Delany, K. (2021). "What challenges will organisations face transitioning for the first time to the new normal of remote working?," *Human Resource Development International*, 1–9. doi:10.1080/13678868.2021.2017391.
- Del Boca, D., N. Oggero, P. Profeta, and M.C. Rossi (2021). Did COVID-19 affect the division of labor within the household? Evidence from two waves of the pandemic in Italy, CEPR Discussion Paper No. DP16257, Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3886726>, Accessed on February 2, 2023.
- Edmans, A. (2011). "Does the stock market fully value intangibles? Employee satisfaction and equity prices", *Journal of Financial Economics*, 101(3), 621–640. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2011.03.021>
- Felstead, A. (2022). Remote Working: A Research Overview. London: Routledge. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003247050>
- Finne, L. B., J.O. Christensen, and S. Knardahl (2016). "Psychological and social work factors as predictors of mental distress and positive affect: A prospective, multilevel study." *PLoS ONE* 11 (3): e0152220. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0152220
- Fuller, S., and C.E. Hirsh (2019). "Family-friendly" jobs and motherhood pay penalties: The impact of flexible work arrangements across the educational spectrum", *Work and Occupations*, 46(1), 3–44. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0730888418771116>
- Gallacher, G., and I. Hossain (2020). "Remote work and employment dynamics under COVID-19: Evidence from Canada", *Canadian Public Policy, Analyse De Politiques*, 46(1), 44–54. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3138/cpp.2020-026>

- Gajendran, R. S., and D.A. Harrison (2007).“The good, the bad, and the unknown about telecommuting: Meta-analysis of psychological mediators and individual consequences”, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(6), 15-24. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.92.6.1524>
- Ghana Health Service 2020.Situation update, Covid-19 outbreak in Ghana as at 7 May (2020) . Accra, Ghana: Retrieved from [https:// ghanahealthservice.org/covid19/archive.php](https://ghanahealthservice.org/covid19/archive.php), Accessed on September 12, 2022.
- Golden, L. and B. Wiens-Tuers (2006). “To your happiness?Extra hours of labour supply and worker well-being”, *The Journal of Socio-Economics*, 35(2), 382–397. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socec.2005.11.039>
- Golden, L., J. Henly and S. Lambert (2014). “Work schedule flexibility: A contributor to employee happiness?”,*Journal of Social Research and Policy*. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2129520>
- Gifford, J. (2022). “Remote working: Unprecedented increase and a developing research agenda”, *Human Resource Development International*, 25(2), 105-113, DOI: 10.1080/13678868.2022.2049108
- Gifford, J., and M. Green (2020). “How could COVID-19 change the world of work?” Retrieved from www.cipd.co.uk/news-views/changing-work-views/future-work/thought-pieces/covid-19-change-work Accessed on February 2, 2023.
- Grant, C. A., L.M. Wallace, and P.C. Spurgeon (2013).“An exploration of the psychological factors affecting remote e-worker’s job effectiveness, well-being and work-life balance”, *Employee Relations*, 35(5), 527–546. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/ER-08-2012-0059>
- Hoeritzauer, M. (2022). “Can businesses dismiss workers who refuse to return to the office?”,*People Management*, Retrieved from <https://www.peoplemanagement.co.uk/experts/legal/can-businessesdismiss-workers-refuse-return-to-office>
- Ingusci, E., F. Signore, M.L. Giancaspro, A. Manuti, M. Molino, and V. Russo (2021).“Workload, techno overload, and behavioral stress during COVID-19 emergency: The role of job crafting in remote workers”, *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 11- 41. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.655148>
- Irawanto, D. W., K.R. Novianti, and K. Roz (2021). “Work from Home: Measuring satisfaction between Work-Life Balance and work stress during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Indonesia”, *Economies*, 9(3), 96. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies9030096>

- Jaeger, P. T., and K.M. Thompson (2003).“E-government around the world: Lessons, challenges, and future directions”, *Government Information Quarterly*, 20, 389-394. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2003.08.001>
- Ko, E. J., A.H. Kim, and S.S. Kim (2021). “Toward the understanding of the appropriation of ICT-based smart-work and its impact on performance in organizations”, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 171, 120994. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120994>
- Lin, C., C. Standing, and Y.C. Liu (2008). “A model to develop effective virtual teams”, *Decision Support Systems*, 45 (4): 1031–1045. DOI:10.1016/j.dss.2008.04.002
- Lockwood, N. R. (2005). “Crisis management in today’s business environment: HR’s strategic role”, *Human Resource Magazine*, 1–10. Retrieved from <https://www.shrm.org/hr-today/news/hr-magazine/documents/1205rquartpdf.pdf>
- Mas, A., and A. Pallais (2017).“Valuing alternative work arrangements”, *American Economic Review*, 107(12), 3722–3759.DOI: 10.1257/aer.20161500
- Moen, P., E.L. Kelly, E. Tranby, and Q. Huang (2011). “Changing work, changing health: can real work-time flexibility promote health behaviors and well-being?”,*Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 52(4), 404–429. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022146511418979>
- National Communications Authority and Ghana Statistical Service (2020) .Household survey on ICT in Ghana, Accra.
- National Information Technology Agency (2014). Ghana e-Government Interoperability Framework, Accra.
- O’Farrell, R., and P. Montagnier (2020) .“Measuring digital platform-mediated workers”, *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 35(1), 130–144. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ntwe.12155>
- Ortiz de Guinea, A., J. Webster, and D.S. Staples (2012) .“A Meta-analysis of the consequences of virtualness on team functioning”, *Information and Management* 49(6): 301–308.doi:10.1016/j.im.2012.08.003.
- President of Ghana (2020a.). President Akufo-Addo Addresses Nation on Updates to Ghana’s Enhanced Response to the Coronavirus Pandemic. Retrieved from <http://presidency.gov.gh/index.php/briefing-room/speeches/1546-president-akufo,addo-addresses-nation-on-updates-to-ghana-senhanced-response-to-the-coronavirus-pandemic>, Accessed on September 13, 2022.

- Republic of Ghana. (2020). Imposition of Restrictions Act 2020 (Act 1012), Accra: Assembly Press. Retrieved from <https://verfassungsblog.de/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Imposition-of-Restrictions-Act-2020-Act-1012.pdf>
- Ruiller, C., B. Van Der Heijden, F. Chedotel, and M. Dumas (2019). “You have got a friend”: The value of perceived proximity for teleworking success in dispersed teams” *Team Performance Management: An International Journal*, 25(1/2), 2–29. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/TPM-11-2017-0069>
- Schlachter, S., A. McDowall, M. Cropley, and I. Inceoglu, (2018). “Voluntary work-related technology use during non-work time: A narrative synthesis of empirical research and research agenda”, *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 20(4): 825–846. doi:10.1111/ijmr.12165. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijmr.12165>
- Wang, B., Y. Liu, J. Qian, and S.K. Parker (2021). “Achieving effective remote working during the COVID-19 pandemic: A work design perspective”, *Applied Psychology*, 70, 16–59 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/apps.12290>
- Wheatley, D., and J. Gifford 2019. “UK working lives: Survey Report (2019).” C. I. o. P. a. Development. <http://cipd.co.uk/workinglives>. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/apps.12290>
- World Health Organization (2020). “Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19),” 94 (April), 1–2. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/situation-reports/20200423-sitrep-94-covid-19.pdf>
- Zou, P., D. Huo, and M. Li (2020b). “The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on firms: a survey in Guangdong Province, China”, *Global Health Research Policy* 5(41).doi: 10.1186/s41256-020-00166-z.